

IMPACT OF HIGH BORON CONCENTRATION ON PLANTS

Urvi Gupta^{1*}, Pradeep Verma² and Hitesh Solanki³

¹Department of Botany, Gujarat University, Gujarat

²Department of Biology, IITE - Gandhinagar, Gandhinagar, Gujarat.

³Department of Botany, Gujarat University, Gujarat

E-mail: urvi8198@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Micronutrients are essential elements utilized by plants for a healthy growth. Each of these elements has a significant role in plant nutrition. Boron is an essential element for plants' development. Adequate B nutrition is critical for quality of crops and high yields. In small concentrations boron compounds are used as micronutrients in fertilizers, in large concentrations it adversely affects the plant growth and can be used as. But there is a narrow range in boron deficiency and toxicity. Present review work focused on the toxic concentration level of boron and its effects on plant growth as well as the methods to overcome the boron toxicity.

Key words : Micro nutrient, Boron, Toxicity, Plant nutrition. .

INTRODUCTION

Boron is one of the essential micronutrient for plants. It is unique among the essential elements in that a narrow range in concentration can mean the difference between plant deficiency and plant toxicity. Whereas a fraction of one part per million may be required, a few parts per million may be toxic to plants (Muntean, 2009). All nutrient elements are required in adequate amount for better growth of plants. But when the amount exceed adequacy it become harmful to plants and known as toxicity. Mineral toxicity is an excess level of any of the minerals essential to plant health. An abnormally high mineral concentration is usually defined as a level that may impair a function on that mineral (Fig-1).

Reduced crop productivity due to soils containing toxic level of Boron is a worldwide problem that can limit plant growth (Nable *et. al.*, 1997). Boron toxicity leads to decreases in

crop yields grown in different regions of the world (Cartwright *et. al.*, 1986). However, despite the importance of this nutritional disorder, it is not understood why B is toxic to plants, or how tolerant plants avoid toxicity (Reid *et. al.*, 2004). It has long been known that the optimum B level for one species could be either toxic or insufficient for other species (Blevins and Lukaszewski, 1998).

Conditions which lead to toxicity:

There are several natural as well as anthropogenic sources which are responsible for boron toxicity. Much of the earlier literature in regard to the toxic effects of boron is reviewed by Brenchley and Winifred in 1927.

The major sources of high B concentration are boron rich soils and ground water or soils exposed to B-rich irrigation water. Irrigation water is the most important contributor to high levels of soil B (Eaton and Frank, 1935; Scofield

et. al., 1931; Nable *et.al.*, 1997; Chauhan and Power, 1978). B level in soils can also be increased by fertilizers (Schreiner *et. al.*, 1920; Nable *et. al.*, 1997), Nutrient solutions used experimentally (Mchargue and Calfee, 1933; Warington, 1923), Sewage sludge or by fly ash (Nable *et. al.*, 1997). Although of considerable agronomic importance, our understanding of B toxicity is rather fragmented and limited (Nable *et. al.*, 1997).

Figure-1: Role of Boron in Plant Metabolism

Boron toxicity, on the other hand, has also been observed, notably in plants growing in arid and semi-arid regions of the world and desert areas where native soil high in boron and low rainfall co-exist. (Marschner, 1995; Muntean, 2009) The highest concentrations of soil B are often concentrated in marine evaporites and in marine argillaceous sediment. (Erd, 1980; Muntean, 2009) Boron is often found in high concentrations in association with saline soils and saline well water (Dhankhar and Dahiya, 1980).

Furthermore, in recent years, B toxicity has attracted increasing interest owing to the greater demand for desalinated water, in which the B concentration may be too high for healthy irrigation (Parks and Edwards, 2005).

Toxicity Symptoms:

Because B accumulates in the leaf margins, an early symptom of excess B is discoloration and eventual death of the leaf margins. It is the

typical visible symptom of B toxicity amongst a wide variety of plant species. Generally it appears on older leaves than younger leaves. Leaf burn – chlorotic and/or necrotic patches at the margins and tips of older leaves occur. Some plants may also develop black spots on older foliage. Normally, discoloration along the whole length of the leaf distinguishes B excess from Ca deficiency, where just the leaf tip and margin at the tip turn brown and die. Due to this crop yield adversely affected. (Paull *et. al.*, 1992; Nable *et. al.*, 1997; Bennett, 1993; Bergmann, 1992; Eaton, 1944; Muntean, 2009; Benton, 1997; Punchana *et. al.*, 2004).

Boron toxicity negatively affects plant growth, which results in reduced vigour, stunted plant growth, delayed development, decreases number, size and weight of fruits and discoloration of leaves. (Paull *et. al.*, 1992; Nable *et. al.*, 1997; Muntean, 2009; Punchana *et. al.*, 2004). Visible symptoms of B toxicity do not appear to develop in roots. As B concentrations in the roots remain relatively low compared to those in leaves, even at very high levels of B supply (Nable, 1988; Oertli and Roth, 1969), perhaps toxic concentrations do not occur in root tissues.

The physiological effects of boron toxicity include reduced root cell division, decreased shoot and root growth (Lovatt and Bates 1984; Nable *et. al.* 1997), decrease in leaf chlorophyll, inhibition of photosynthesis, lower stomatal conductance (Lovatt and Bates 1984), deposition of lignin and suberin (Ajay Singh *et al.*, 2013 and Ghanati *et. al.*, 2002), reduced proton extrusion from roots (Roldan *et. al.*, 1992), increased membrane leakiness, peroxidation of lipids and altered activities of antioxidation pathways (Karabal *et. al.*, 2003). These toxicity symptoms are slow to develop, or are only observed with extreme B treatments.

Method to overcome Boron toxicity:

There is a narrow margin between boron deficiency and toxicity in some plants; however, the risk of inducing toxicity should not be ignored. There are several ways by which B toxicity can be reduced.

As boron is easily leached from soil it can be removed from soils through the leaching action of water passing through and below the active plant root zone. It is at times necessary to treat high boron soils that are alkaline with soil acidifying amendments like elemental sulfur prior to the leaching process. (Muntean, 2009).

It has been suggested that an antioxidant response may reduce B-toxicity damage in some plants (Gunes *et. al.*, 2006). This antioxidant response is considered to be a critical process for protecting plants against oxidative damage in combination with a wide range of environmental factors (Inze´ and Montagu, 1995), including UV-light excess, salinity, drought, heavy metals, chilling, oxygen shortage and nutritional deprivation (Mittler, 2002).

Allelopathic interaction between nutrients elements can also be very useful in reducing toxic level of B. Boron toxicity can be decreased with P x B interaction (Gunes *et. al.*, 1999), also high level of N decreases the B concentration (Alpaslan *et. al.*, 1996). Under some circumstances it may be possible to alleviate B toxicity in plants by applying Zn to soils or as a foliar spray to affected plants (Graham *et. al.*, 1986 and Swietlik, 1995).

The toxic effect of boron was observed to be alleviated by calcium application, particularly at 10 and 20 mg B kg⁻¹ levels, suggesting the negative impact of Ca on B availability, in agreement of the statement of by Gupta (1972) and Taban *et. al.* (1995). Ca counteracted the toxic effect of B, and result in higher dry weight of B treated plants. These results agreed with Chatterjee *et. al.* (1987), Taban *et. al.* (1995) and Turan *et. al.* (2009). One of structural element in plant cell wall is Ca. Calcium bounded with pectin molecules and localized in the cell wall as Ca-pectate complexes which may act to stabilize boron in cell wall (Yamaouchi *et. al.*, 1986, Cleland *et. al.*, 1990).

REFERENCES

1. **Ajay Singh, J. P. Shahi and D. M. Langade**, 2013. Appraisal of heterosis for

yield and yield attributing components in maize (*Zea mays* L.). *Biolife*. 1(3); 123-129.

2. **Alpaslan, M., Taban, S., Inal, A., Kütük, C., and Erdal, I.** 1996. Boron- nitrogen relationships in wheat which grown nutrient solution. Pamukkale Univ. Faculty of Engineering. *Journal of Engineering Science*; 2 (3): 215- 219, (in Turkish).
3. **Bennett, W. F.** 1993. Plant Nutrient Utilization and Diagnostic Plant Symptoms, In: *Nutrient Deficiencies and Toxicities in Crop Plants*. The American Phytopathological Society, St. Paul Minnesota, pp. 1-7. ISBN.0-89054-151-5.
4. **Benton, J. J.** 1997. *Hydroponics: a practical guide for the soilless grower*. St. Lucie Press, Boca Raton, FL. Pp: 30-38, 52, 53. ISBN: 0-8493-3167-6.
5. **Bergmann, W.** 1992. *Nutritional disorders of plants. Development, visual and analytical diagnosis*. Gustav Fisher Verlag Jena, New York, USA. Pp 204–239. ISBN: 3827406323.
6. **Blevins, D. G., and Lukaszewski**, 1998. Boron in plant structure and function. *Annual Review of Plant Physiology and Plant Molecular Biology*; 49: 481-500.
7. **Brenchley, and Winifred, E.** 1927. *Inorganic plant poisons and stimulants*. 2nd edition, Cambridge University Press.
8. **Cartwright, B., Zarcinas, B. A., and Spouncer, L. A.** 1986. Boron toxicity in South Australian barley crops. *Aust. J. Agric. Res.*; 37: 351–359.
9. **Chatterjee, C., Sinha, P., Nautical, N., Agarwala, S. C., and Sharma, C. P.** 1987. Metabolic changes associated with boron calcium interaction in maize. *Soil Sci. Plant Nutr.*; 33: 607- 617.
10. **Chauhan, R. P. S. and Powar, S. L.** 1978. Tolerance of wheat and pea to boron in irrigation water. *Plant and Soil*; 50: 145–149.
11. **Cleland, R. E., Virk, S. S., Taylor, D., and Bjorkman, T.** 1990. Calcium, cell walls and growth. In Leonard RT, Hepler PK: Calcium in plant growth and development. *Am.Soc. Plant Physiol. Symp.*; 4: 9-16.
12. **Dhankhar, D. P., and Dahiya, S. S.** 1980. The effect of different levels of boron and soil salinity on the yield of dry matter and its

- mineral composition in Ber (*Zizyphus rotundifolia*). *Int. Symp. on Salt Affected Soils*. Karnal, India, pp 396–403.
13. **Eaton, and Frank, M.** 1935. Boron in soils and irrigation waters and its effect on plants, with particular reference to the San Joaquin Valley of California. *U. S. Dept. Agr. Tech. Bull.*;448.
 14. **Eaton, F. M.** 1944. Deficiency, toxicity and accumulation of boron in plants. *J. Agric. Res.*; 69: 237–277.
 15. **Erd, R. C.** 1980. *The minerals of boron*. In Mellor's Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry. Suppl. to Vol. V. Ed. Thompson R.: 7–71. Longman, New York.
 16. **Ghanati, F., Morita, A., and Yokota, H.** 2002. Induction of suberin and increase of lignin content by excess Boron in Tobacco cell. *Soil Sci. Plant Nutr.*; 48(3): 357–364.
 17. **Graham, R. D., Welch, R. M., Grunes, D. L., Cary, E. E., and Norvell, W. A.** 1986. Effect of zinc deficiency on the accumulation of boron and other mineral nutrients in barley. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.*; 51: 652–657.
 18. **Gunes, A., Alpaslan, M., Cikili, Y., Ozcan, H.** 1999. Effect of zinc on the alleviation of boron toxicity in tomato. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*; 22: 1061–1068.
 19. **Gunes, A., Soylemezoglu, G., Inal, A., Bagci, E. G., Coban, S. and Sahin, O.** 2006. Antioxidant and stomatal responses of grapevine (*Vitis vinifera* L.) to boron toxicity. *Scientia Horticulturae*; 110:279–284.
 20. **Gupta, U. C.** 1972. Interaction effects of boron and lime on barley. *Soil Sci. Soc. Amer. Proc.*; 36: 332–334.
 21. http://www.cropscience.org.au/icsc2004/poster/2/5/5/899_punchanas.htm (Retrieved on 13th February, 2010 at 9:30am).
 22. **Inze, D., Montagu, V. M.** 1995. Oxidative stress in plants. *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*; 6: 153–158.
 23. **Karabal, E., Yu' cel, M., O' kte, H. A.** 2003. Antioxidants responses of tolerant and sensitive barley cultivars to boron toxicity. *Plant Science*; 164: 925–933.
 24. **Lovatt, C. J., and Bates, L. M.** 1984. Early effects of excess boron on photosynthesis and growth of *Cucurbita pepo*. *J. Exp. Bot.*; 35: 297–305.
 25. **Marschner, H.** 1995. Boron. *Mineral Nutrition of Higher Plants.*; 2: 379 - 396. Academic Press San Diego.
 26. **Mchargue, J. S., and Calfee, R. K.** 1933. Further evidence that boron is essential for the growth of lettuce. *Plant Physiol.*; 8: 305–313.
 27. **Mittler, R.** 2002. Oxidative stress, antioxidants and stress tolerance. *Trends in Plant Science*; 7: 405–410.
 28. **Muntean, D. W.** 2009. Boron, the overlooked essential element. Soil and Plant Laboratory Inc. P.O Box 1648 Bellevue, WA 98009. <http://www.soilandplantlaboratory.com/pdf/articles/BoronOverlookedEssential.pdf> (Retrieved on 29th April, 2010 at 12:55pm).
 29. **Nable, R. O.** 1988. Resistance to boron toxicity amongst several barley and wheat cultivars: a preliminary examination of the resistance mechanism. *Plant and Soil*; 112: 45–57.
 30. **Nable, R. O., Bañuelos, G. S. and Paull, J. G.** 1997. Boron toxicity. *Plant and Soil*, Chapter 12; 193: 181–198.
 31. **Oertli, J. J., and Roth, J. A.** 1969. Boron nutrition of sugar beet, cotton, and soybean. *Agron. J.*; 61:191–95.
 32. **Parks, J. L., and Edwards, M.** 2005. Boron in the environment. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Biotechnology*; 35: 81–114
 33. **Paull, J. G., Nable, R. O., and Rathjen, A. J.** 1992. Physiological and genetic control of the tolerance of wheat to high concentrations of boron and implications for plant breeding. *Plant and Soil*; 146: 251–260.
 34. **Punchana, S., Jamjod, S., and Rerkasem, B.** 2004. Response to boron toxicity in boron efficient and inefficient wheat genotypes. 4th International Crop Science Congress.
 35. **Reid, R. J., Hayes, J. E., Post, A., Stangoulis, J. C. R. and Graham, R. D.** 2004. A critical analysis of the causes of boron toxicity in plants. *Plant, Cell and Environment*; 27(11): 1405–1414.
 36. **Roldan, M., Belver, A., Rodriguez-Rosales, M. P., Ferrol, N., and Donaire, J.**

- P. 1992. In vivo and in vitro effects of boron on the plasma membrane proton pump of sunflower roots. *Physiol Plant*; 84:49-54.
37. **Schreiner, Oswald, Brown, B. E., Skinner, J. J. and Shapovalov, M.** 1920. Crop injury by borax in fertilizers. *U. S. Dept. Agr. Dept. Circ.*; 84.
38. **Scofield, Carl, S., and Wilcox, L. V.** 1931. Boron in irrigation waters. *U.S. Dept. Agr. Tech. Bull.*; 264.
39. **Swietlik, D.** 1995. Interaction between zinc deficiency and boron toxicity on growth and mineral nutrition of sour orange seedlings. *J. Plant Nutrition*;18:1191–1207.
40. **Taban, S., Alpaslan, M., Kutuk, C., Inal, A., and Erdal, I.** 1995. Relationship between boron and calcium on wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). 9th International Symposium of CIEC, “Soil fertility and fertilization management-bridge between science, industry and practice”, September 25-30, Kuşadası-Turkey. Pp: 85-90.
41. **Turan, M. A., Taban, N., Taban, S.** 2009. Effect of Calcium on the Alleviation of Boron Toxicity and Localization of Boron and Calcium in Cell Wall of Wheat. *Not. Bot. Hort. Agrobot. Cluj*; 37 (2): 99-103.
42. **Warrington, K.** 1923. The effect of boric acid and borax on the broad bean and certain other plants. *Annals of Botany.*; 37: 629-672.
43. **Yamaouchi, M., Hara, T., and Sonoda, Y.** 1986. Distribution of calcium and boron in the pectin fraction of tomato leaf cell wall. *Plant Cell Physiol.*; 27: 729-732.

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7214159>

Received: 9 April 2014;

Accepted; 23 May 2014;

Available online : 15 June 2014